
10 things you should know about preprints

This month marks the 10th anniversary of [bioRxiv](https://doi.org/10.1101/2010.01.01.100001), a significant milestone for the biology preprint server that has revolutionized the way biologists share their research. Here are 10 key things you should know about it.

[Happy birthday bioRxiv!](#)

1. Preprints enable you to share your science at an earlier stage

The preprint movement is often referred to as ASAPbio, or “As Soon As Possible” biology. After all, the purpose of publishing is to communicate your scientific work, with the hope that it will inspire others to build upon it and achieve further advancements. Preprints expedite this communal cycle, allowing the wheel of progress to spin more rapidly, benefitting society and everyone involved.

➤ ASAPbioASAPbio.org

Post your preprint in 5 steps

- 1. Get your co-authors on board**

Any questions? Check the preprint resources available at asapbio.org/preprint-info.
- 2. Choose a server**

A list of preprint servers is available at asapbio.org/preprint-servers. Consider where to post according to the type of paper (primary research, narrative review), disciplinary scope, server visibility and indexing.
- 3. Check journal policies**

A large majority of journals in life sciences accept preprints. Information on policies related to preprints at a range of publishers is available on [Wikipedia](#).
- 4. Choose a license**

Check the [ASAPbio licensing FAQ](#) for information on copyright and license options for preprints.
- 5. Prepare your manuscript**

Prepare the paper per the preprint server's guidelines, taking as much care as for journal submission. Upload any code/data/reagents you want to share to appropriate repositories.

Post the preprint!

Share it with colleagues via social media or email

[Preprinting in 5 easy steps /via ASAPbio.org.](#)

2. Preprints are citable and should be cited

Because they are assigned a DOI, preprints become permanent fixtures on the internet and can be cited in formal academic publications. Furthermore, it is essential to acknowledge preprints through citation. Citation serves not only as a means to substantiate factual claims from the literature but also as a way to attribute the original source of a dataset, resource, or even an idea. Citing sources is also an ethical imperative; if you have derived information from the literature, it is your responsibility to provide proper attribution. Neglecting to do so may be perceived as a breach of scientific integrity.

3. Preprinting is not a movement against peer review

There's a common misconception that preprint advocates are against peer review, but this notion is unfounded. What many preprint advocates oppose is [a specific form of peer review known as pre-publication peer review](#)—a non-transparent system that is often susceptible to manipulation. How else can we explain that clearly flawed scientific work is regularly published in some of the leading journals?

4. Anyone can review preprints

Preprint advocates argue for an alternative approach to peer review, wherein papers are first preprinted, made available for everyone to examine and provide feedback on. In fact, the next significant development in the preprint movement is the integration of preprint peer review. Sign up and participate in [crowd review initiatives](#) to provide valuable feedback to preprint authors!

[Crowd preprint review is back! Sign up to participate in one of several groups led by ASAPbio Fellows.](#)

5. Preprints can be copied and redistributed

Preprints can be freely copied and redistributed, providing a distinct advantage over journal publications. Journals often impose copyright restrictions, making it cumbersome for others to reproduce figures and datasets, even when full credit to the authors is intended. One might question why journals enforce such limits, given that it is the authors who create the work and figures in the first place. Preprints offer a solution by allowing you to sidestep these journal copyrights. When you preprint your work under licenses like CC-BY (Creative Commons Attribution), you grant permission for others to reuse the material, provided they give proper citation to the source. This remains applicable even if the preprint is subsequently published in a journal. This is a significant stride in favor of open access and information sharing, challenging the practices of commercial publishers.

6. Preprints are free to publish and free to read

If you support open science, you should embrace preprints. In an era of exorbitant Article Processing Charges (APCs), where publishing a single article can cost as much as supporting a PhD student, it's crucial to emphasize that preprints are entirely free. This accessibility empowers scientists, particularly those in the global south and with constrained budgets, to freely disseminate their research. And let's not be fooled into thinking that APCs don't ultimately come out of our own pockets. Whether through direct payment or University allocation, APCs still impacts us as taxpayers and consumes a portion of our research funders' limited budgets, which could otherwise be dedicated to supporting research and researchers.

7. Funders should mandate preprints

[Plan U](#) calls for funders to mandate the use of preprints. This is a forward-thinking policy that is [starting to take hold in one form or another](#). By requiring researchers to share their work through preprints, funders can promote greater transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in the scientific community. This move not only maximizes the impact of funded research but also ensures that valuable research findings reach a wider audience without the barriers of journal paywalls. Ultimately, mandating preprints aligns with the principles of open science and helps optimize the allocation of research funds towards the advancement of knowledge rather than publishing costs.

#PlanU #sciencebigidea mandate preprints. Publish and filter.
@npariente #NordicEMBL #ASAPbio

The image shows a screenshot of a PLOS Biology article titled "Plan U: Universal access to scientific and medical research via funder preprint mandates" by Richard Sever, Michael Eisen, and John Inglis, published June 4, 2019. A blue callout box highlights the article's key message: "decoupling the dissemination of manuscripts from the much slower process of evaluation and certification by journals, preprints [...] accelerate the pace of research [...]. If all funding agencies were to mandate posting of preprints by grantees—an approach we term Plan U (for 'universal')—free access to the world's scientific output for everyone would be achieved with minimal effort". To the right, a video call inset shows a woman with glasses speaking.

[Plan U: one of science big ideas](#). Plan U was articulated in this 2019 PLOS Biology article by [Richard Sever, Mike Eisen, and John Inglis](#).

8. Preprints should not be published when the paper is accepted

Don't be a [#LatePreprinter](#), someone who posts a preprint after it has already been accepted by a journal. Some even wait for a positive evaluation and quasi-acceptance before posting the preprint. This can be seen as merely checking a box to give the appearance of supporting

preprints or fulfilling funder mandates, without genuinely embracing the core principles of preprinting. It's worth noting that this practice goes against the guidelines set by bioRxiv, [which permit submission at any point before journal acceptance but explicitly prohibit post-acceptance submissions](#).

Sophien Kamoun @KamounLab · May 26, 2022

Time for a new hashtag **#LatePreprinter** a scientist who posts a **preprint** after it was **accepted** by a journal.

A phenomenon worth studying id say...

Devang Mehta @drdevangm · May 26, 2022

I honestly think one of the stupidest thing (usually older PIs) do is only post their preprints after they've been accepted by a journal. And I'm not being hyperbolic, it's just plain stupid.

[#LatePreprinter](#)

9. Preprints should include the supporting data

Preprints should unequivocally incorporate links to their supporting data, and preprint servers like bioRxiv could play a more proactive role in ensuring this practice. [It can be exasperating to peruse a preprint and find no convenient access to the underlying data](#). Consider, for instance, the futility of reading a genome paper without the ability to query the genome itself. To rectify this issue, [a straightforward checkbox system could be implemented to enforce the inclusion of supporting data with preprints](#). This would not only enhance the transparency and credibility of the research but also facilitate the replication and further exploration of the findings by the scientific community.

Ahmet Bakirbas @plantbiol · Nov 3, 2020

It's upsetting to see preprints where authors give no access to their supplemental tables, no links to browse their data and/or make their raw data private on SRA. Now, the reader has to wait for the peer-reviewed version as if there is no preprint to begin with.

Sebastian Schornack @dromius · Nov 2, 2020

Potentially interesting preprint on tissue specificity of leaf stress responses from @whelan_lab. Unfortunately I cannot find the supplementary tables... @biorxiv_plants twitter.com/biorxiv_plants...

Sebastian Schornack
@dromius

I think this is a failure of the @Biorxiv preprint formal acceptance process. It should be easy to detect whether the occurrence of the string "suppl" within any manuscript is accompanied by actual supplementary data.

[bioRxiv: Show me the data.](#)

10. You can preprint anything you want

People, you can preprint virtually anything you wish to disseminate to the scientific community, and get credit for it. While bioRxiv is widely known for full-length research papers, it's essential to recognize that there is a broader preprint landscape for other academic outputs. For materials such as review articles, posters, and datasets, [Zenodo, a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program](#), offers an excellent alternative platform. Zenodo provides an ideal space to share a diverse range of scientific content, and allows researchers to maximize the visibility and accessibility of their work, encouraging collaboration and knowledge sharing across a multitude of scientific disciplines.

Sophien Kamoun @KamounLab
#2023ISMPMI Why not publish your poster on @ZENODO_ORG and assign it a doi just like Mau @mpcontreras4 did zenodo.org/record/8146518

Poster

Open Access

Mauricio Contreras @mpcontreras4 · 4h
If you're at #2023ISMPMI, come talk to me about NLR networks and bioengineering on Monday!
P168 in Immune Receptors II session
(12.30 to 13.15pm)
Looking forward to some good discussions! 😊

#MPMI2019Posters

We published the Kamoun Lab posters presented at #ICMPMI2019 Congress on Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions, Glasgow, July 14-18, on @ZENODO_ORG.

Kudos to all authors for their amazing contributions!

Joe Win, Mauricio Contreras, Benjamin Petre, Tolga O Bozkurt, Martin H Schattat, Jan Sklenar, ... **Sophien Kamoun**. (2019). Host-interactor screens of RXLR effectors reveal plant processes manipulated by Phytophthora. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3351297>

Mauricio Contreras, Benjamin Petre, Tolga Bozkurt, Joe Win, & **Sophien Kamoun**. (2019). Phytophthora RXLR-WY effectors cooperate to modulate host vesicle trafficking. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3349841>

Erin Zess, Yasin Dagdas, Abbas Maqbool, Tolga O Bozkurt, Mark Banfield, & **Sophien Kamoun**. (2019). Effector adaptation in a host-specialized lineage of Phytophthora. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3349901>

Chih-Hang Wu, & **Sophien Kamoun**. (2019). A genetically unlinked NLR network that modulates plant immunity against diverse pathogens originated from an ancestral gene cluster. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3350801>

[Why you should publish your posters.](#)

11. [Bonus point: Preprinting enables you to celebrate twice!](#)

Sophien Kamoun @KamounLab · Oct 31, 2019 ...

One major benefit of [@biorxivpreprint](#) is that you get to celebrate with a cake when you post the **preprint** and then one more time when the paper is formally **accepted**... [#ASAPbio](#)

Chih-Hang Wu @AdamWu9527 · Oct 31, 2019

It was great to put a paper together with @HiroakiAdachi3, @delaconcepcionj @rcastellsg and @vladnekrasov on our NRC CRISPRed tomato and benth. Time for a cake now. @KamounLab

[11. Bonus point: Preprinting enables you to celebrate twice!](#)

Acknowledgements

I'm grateful to the colleagues whose tweets inspired this article. I dedicate this post to the bioRxiv Team and wish them the best for their 10 year anniversary. This post was written with assistance from [ChatGPT](#).

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Jul 12, 2022

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Humor can help bring focus to serious topics. Controls, controls, and more controls...

. . .

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